

Non-nitrogenous Constituents of *Fumaria indica* (Haussk) Pugsley

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Manuscript received 29 November 1972; revised 7 December 1972; accepted 6 February 1973

THE *Fumaria* species commonly available in India under the name 'Shehterah' or 'Pit-papra' was identified by Pugsley¹ as *Fumaria indica* (Haussk) (Papaveraceae), and not as *F. officinalis* or *F. parviflora*², which are, however, the common fumitory of Europe. From the Indian species of *Fumaria*, pentatriacontane, C₃₅H₇₂, m.p. 75°–76°, and protopine were isolated by Agarwal³, and ceryl alcohol and protopine by Govindachari⁴, whereas nine alkaloids were isolated and identified by Manske⁵ from *F. officinalis* of European origin.

In view of the above different reports, a reinvestigation of the Indian species was undertaken. Isolation and identification of four neutral compounds from the petroleum ether extract of *F. indica* are reported here. In addition, seven isoquinoline alkaloids have also been isolated and characterised, and will be reported separately.

Experimental

The petroleum ether extractive (93.5 g) after separation of alkaloidal constituents from dried and milled whole plant of *Fumaria indica* (4 kg), collected locally from Punjab⁶, was saponified with strong alkali and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract on concentration yielded a colourless crystalline solid (A, 12.38 g), and a non-crystalline residue (B, 15.45 g). (A) appeared to be a major compound of *R_f* 0.49 with traces of a second compound of *R_f* 0.01, which could not be separated by crystallisation. Individual components were isolated by chromatographic resolution of (A) and (B) over Brockmann neutral aluminium oxide, monitoring at every stage by thin layer chromatography over silica gel G chromatoplates, using C₆H₆ : CHCl₃ (1 : 1) as developer and AC₂O : H₂SO₄ : ETOH (5 : 5 : 90) or I₂ vapour for the staining.

19-Methyl-Octacosan-1-ol: The petroleum ether (60°–80°): benzene (1 : 1) eluates from the chromatographic resolution of solid A over alumina afforded shining granules (10.83 g, acetone) of 19-methyl-octacosan-1-ol, C₂₉H₆₀O, m.p. 84°–85°, *R_f* 0.49; no colour reaction with Liebermann-Burchard reagent; i.r. ν_{max} 3250–3350 (OH) cm⁻¹; n.m.r. δ 1.3–1.4 (25 CH₂ protons), 0.9 (2 CH₃-C), and 3.6 (–CH₂-OH); m/e 423 (M–1, 7%), 407 (80%), 406 (M–H₂O, 100%), 378 [m/e 406–(CH₂ = CH₂), 12%], 297 (84%), 155 (31%), 127 (15%), 125 (42%), indicating a branching of the chain at C₁₉ with a methyl substituent (Found : C, 81.72, 81.87; H, 14.74, 14.44; C–CH₃, 6.66, 8.68. C₂₉H₆₀O requires C, 81.99; H, 14.24; 2C–CH₃, 7.07%).

Acetate, shining plates, m.p. 43°, *R_f* 0.94; m/e 423 (M–COCH₃), 406 (M–CH₃COOH), 378 [M–CH₃COOH–(CH₂ = CH₂)], 339 [M–CH₃(CH₂)₇CH₂], 311 [M–CH₃(CH₂)₈CH₂CH₃], 155 [CH₃(CH₂)₈CH₂CH₃], 127 [CH₃(CH₂)₇CH₂CH₃], 43 (CH₃.C ≡ O⁺) (Found : C, 80.15, 80.20; H, 13.11, 13.40; C–CH₃, 7.41, 8.29. C₂₉H₅₈O.COCH₃ requires C, 79.82; H, 13.30; 3C–CH₃, 9.65%).

C₂₇–C₂₉ *n*-Alkanes: The petroleum ether (60°–80°) eluates from the chromatographic resolution of the non-crystallisable residue (B) over alumina yielded shining granules of a mixture of C₂₇–C₂₉ *n*-alkanes (840 mg, acetone), m.p. 62°–64°, *R_f* 1.0; no colour with L–B reagent; i.r. no OH absorption; n.m.r. δ 1.25 [–(CH₂)_{*n*}–, strong]; m/e 409, 408 (100%, M⁺ for C₂₉H₆₀), 395, 394 (23%, M⁺ for C₂₈H₅₈), 381, 380 (84%, M⁺ for C₂₇H₅₆), and then peaks corresponding to (M–*n* 14) with 1 and 2 mass units less (Found : C, 85.38, 85.32; H, 14.50, 14.92; C–CH₃, 3.36, 4.92. Calcd. for C₂₉H₆₀ : C, 85.20; H, 14.80; 2C–CH₃, 7.35. C₂₇H₅₆ : C, 85.17; H, 14.83%).

Sterols: The benzene:chloroform (1 : 1) eluates of (B) yielded on crystallisation from alcohol a typical mixture of β -sitosterol, stigmaterol and campesterol in the approximate proportion of 4 : 2 : 1 (as exhibited by mass spectrum) (needles, 600 mg), m.p. 133°–135°, *R_f* 0.19; pink to blue to green colour with L–B reagent; i.r. ν_{max} 3300–3400 (OH) cm⁻¹; typical n.m.r. signals in the aliphatic zone δ 0.7–2.4, 3.5–3.6; m/e 414 (100%), 412 (52%), 400 (24%), and other significant mass peaks consistent with the fragmentation pattern expected of Δ^5 - 3β -sterols⁷.

3-Methyl-Octacosan-1,3-diol: The residue from the chloroform eluates of (B) on crystallisation from alcohol afforded 3-methyl-octacosan-1,3-diol (granules, 115 mg), C₂₉H₆₀O₂, m.p. 92°–94°, *R_f* 0.028; no colour with L–B reagent; i.r. ν_{max} 3250–3400 (OH), 722 (CH₂ rocking) cm⁻¹; n.m.r. δ 3.6 (–CH₂-OH), 1.3 (25 CH₂ protons), 0.9 (2C–CH₃); m/e 422 (M–H₂O, 6%), 404 (M–2H₂O, 21%), 394 [m/e 422–(CH₂ = CH₂), 13%], 376 [M–2H₂O–(CH₂ = CH₂), 17%], 351 (9%), 337 (52%), 309 (100%), 295 (36%), 267 (30%), 197 (42%), 155 (91%), even-numbered homologous mass peaks (M–2H₂O–*n* 28) at m/e 376, 348, 320, 292, 264, 236, 208, 180, 152, 124, 96, 68, 40 (low), showing the presence of a straight chain extending upto 25 C atoms, and then substituents (OH and CH₃) at C₂₈ (Found : C, 78.57, 79.01; H, 14.21, 13.93; C–CH₃, 7.23, 7.71. C₂₉H₆₀O₂ requires C, 79.02; H, 13.72; 2C–CH₃, 6.80%); amorphous *mono*-acetate, *R_f* 0.0, m/e 464 (M–H₂O), 421 (M–H₂O–COCH₃), 404 (M–H₂O–CH₃COOH) indicating the presence of one primary OH (easily acylable) and one tertiary OH (not easily acylable) group in the diol.

Discussion

The present chemical and spectroscopic studies have revealed that pentatriacontane, C₃₅H₇₂, reported by Agarwal³ to be present in the Indian species of *Fumaria*, is, in fact, a mixture of C₂₇–C₂₉ *n*-alkanes, while the reported ceryl alcohol⁴ is a branched chain alkanol, e.g., 19-methyl-octacosan-1-ol. In addition to these, a new branched chain 1 : 3 diol, viz.,

3-methyl-octacosan-1,3-diol, has also been isolated in the present investigation.

Thus, while the alkanes of *F. indica* consist of a mixture of C_{27} , C_{28} and C_{29} *n*-alkanes with C_{27} and C_{29} predominating, the alkanol and alkane diol consist of mass spectrometrically homogeneous branched C_{29} components not apparently derived, in this species, from reduction of the corresponding carboxylic acid according to the tenets of biogenesis⁸ of C_{27} and C_{29} *n*-alkanes.

The co-occurrence of the alkanol, $C_{29}H_{60}O$, and the alkane diol, $C_{29}H_{60}O_2$, in *F. indica* having methyl substituents at different positions, is an example of non-specific methylation pattern in plant species involving carbonyl centres (instead of carbanion centres) of the corresponding C_{28} -poly β -keto chain. These two compounds would act as markers in chemotaxonomic studies of plants belonging to the sub-family *Fumariaceae*, as these are stable secondary end products.

Microanalyses were done by C.D.R.I., Lucknow and by Dr. F. B. Strauss, Oxford, IR (nujol), NMR ($CDCl_3$) and mass spectra were recorded in National Chemical Laboratory, Poona.

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Synthesis of Methylene Bis-(2,4-Dihydroxy Quinolines)

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Manuscript received 2 June 1969; revised 3 July 1972; accepted 12 July 1972

THE interaction study of hydroxymethane sulphonate with cyanacet anilides was undertaken to prepare methylene bisderivatives, with a view to synthesis diquinolylmethanes. In earlier communications methylene bis-derivatives¹ of acetoacet anilides and their cyclised products² were reported. In the present investigation cyanacetanilides (I) are allowed to react with sodium hydroxy methane sulphonate, forming the corresponding methylene bis-derivatives (II), which undergo, simultaneous partial hydrolysis and cyclisation with PPA. (3,4,5), giving 3,3'-methylene bis-(2,4-quinolinediols) (III), the course of reaction is expressed as :

(where, R = phenyl, tolyl, xylyl or naphthyl group).

Experimental

The required methylene bis-derivatives of the substituted amides of cyanacetic acid are prepared as under :

(I) *Methylene bis(cyanacetanilide)*: Cyanacetanilide (0.02M) dissolved in 90% methanol to which was added solution of sodium hydroxymethane sulphonate

TABLE I—METHYLENE BIS-(HYDROXYQUINOLINES)

T = (2,2', 4,4'-Tetrahydroxy-)

Q = (-3,3'-Diquinolylmethane)

B = (-3,3'-Dibenzoquinolylmethane)

Sr. No.	Compound	Molecular formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen %		Carbon %		Hydrogen %	
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	T-Q	$C_{19}H_{14}O_4N_2$	400	41.6	8.59	8.38	68.03	68.25	4.32	4.22
2.	T-8,8'-dichloro-Q	$C_{19}H_{12}O_4N_2Cl_2$	400	48.7	6.93	6.95	—	—	—	—
3.	T-6,6'-dichloro-Q	$C_{19}H_{12}O_4N_2Cl_2$	400	52.5	6.44	6.95	59.11	59.55	2.66	2.97
4.	T-7,7'-dimethyl-Q	$C_{21}H_{18}O_4N_2$	400	36.1	7.81	7.73	69.25	69.60	5.42	5.00
5.	T-6,6--dimethyl-Q	$C_{21}H_{18}O_4N_2$	400	41.7	8.10	7.73	—	—	—	—
6.	T-6,6'-8,8'-tetramethyl-Q	$C_{23}H_{22}O_4N_2$	400	48.0	7.54	7.18	—	—	—	—
7.	T-6,6', 7,7'-tetramethylQ	$C_{23}H_{22}O_4N_2$	400	50.9	7.33	7.18	70.28	70.75	5.62	5.68
8.	T-B-(7 : 8)	$C_{27}H_{18}O_7N_2$	400	48.6	6.31	6.45	—	—	—	—
9.	T-B-(5 : 6)	$C_{27}H_{18}O_4N_2$	400	46.3	6.11	6.45	—	—	—	—